

A Study of Identity and Displacement in Amitav Ghosh's 'The Circle of Reason'

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Abstract:

Amitav Ghosh's debut novel, The Circle of Reason, takes the reader on an intricate journey through themes of displacement, identity, cultural hybridity, and political turmoil. The novel explores the lives of its characters against a backdrop of social and historical upheaval, offering a multifaceted examination of how individuals navigate the forces of modernity and tradition. At the heart of the narrative is the journey of the protagonist, Alu, whose quest for truth and meaning becomes symbolic of the broader tensions of post-colonial societies.

Through its vivid portrayal of diverse cultural landscapes and complex social systems, The Circle of Reason challenges traditional narratives and offers a critique of both colonial history and contemporary globalizing forces. Ghosh's exploration of the intersections between East and West, science and superstition, and the individual and the collective draws attention to the tensions that define our modern existence.

This article provides a critical analysis of Amitav Ghosh's The Circle of Reason, focusing on its exploration of identity, displacement, and cultural hybridity. Through a narrative that spans across multiple countries and cultures, Ghosh constructs a complex dialogue between tradition and modernity, colonial legacies and post-colonial realities, and personal and collective histories. The novel's distinctive approach to storytelling, interweaving history, politics, and myth, invites readers to consider the global dynamics shaping the individual experience in the postcolonial world. This study aims to critically engage with the thematic undercurrents of The Circle of Reason and examine its relevance in understanding the processes of globalization and the construction of identity in contemporary society.

Keywords: history, politics, myth, global dynamics, The Circle of Reason, identity, colonial legacy, post-colonial realities etc.

Introduction

In *The Circle of Reason* (1986), Amitav Ghosh delves into themes of identity and displacement through the life of its protagonist, Nachiketa Bose, better known as Alu. Alu's story begins in the small village of Lalpukur, where, at a young age, he is orphaned and taken in by his uncle, Balaram. The narrative explores Alu's journey from his childhood, marked by personal tragedy and confusion, to a series of escapades that take him across continents, from India to the Middle East and Northern Africa. Through these experiences, Alu becomes a symbol of identity in flux, caught between the individual and collective forces that shape his life. Aijaz Ahmad (1992) highlights *The Circle of Reason* as a significant postcolonial narrative that challenges fixed notions of identity and belonging. The novel's emphasis on transnational movement and cultural intersections reflects the fluidity of identities shaped by colonial and postcolonial histories. Ahmad argues that Ghosh's characters are emblematic of the diasporic condition, constantly negotiating their existence in a globalized world.

Alu's identity is not just a matter of personal self-realization but is also deeply tied to the societal and historical contexts he inhabits. His uncle, Balaram, gives him the name "Alu" or "potato" due to the bumps on his head, a physical anomaly that becomes emblematic of his outsider status and his journey toward self-discovery. His unique appearance and intelligence, as well as his exceptional weaving skills, highlight the complexities of identity in a world where cultural, familial, and social influences often blur the lines of self-understanding.

Alu's journey away from home symbolizes the broader theme of displacement. The phrenological experiments conducted by Balaram on Alu's head, which focus on the supposed mapping of his skull to determine his character, add an element of absurdity to his journey. The idea of the "lumps and swellings" on his skull that refuse to conform to identifiable structures can be read as a metaphor for Alu's fractured sense of self. Ghosh cleverly uses this to illustrate the complexities of identity—one that is neither fixed nor easily understood, especially in the face of the broader societal and political pressures that Alu encounters.

As Alu flees from India, pursued by a determined police officer, Jyothi Das, who wrongly associates him with a terrorist attack, the novel presents a layered exploration of identity. Alu's displacement is not only physical but also psychological, as he grapples with his own understanding of who he is amidst the chaos of the world around him. His journey reflects

the disorienting experience of being displaced, both from his homeland and from a coherent sense of identity.

Through Alu's personal odyssey, *The Circle of Reason* offers a rich commentary on the nature of identity and displacement in a globalized world, where people often find themselves caught between their past and an uncertain future, trying to reconcile personal aspirations with the often rigid constructs of national and cultural identities. Ghosh's narrative thus challenges conventional notions of identity, emphasizing the fluid and ever-changing nature of selfhood in the face of both internal and external forces.

The novel essentially narrates three distinct stories. The initial section addresses the narrative of Balram. He is a rationalist influenced by the biography of Louis Pasteur. His idealism is so extreme that it borders on inhumanity. He has no involvement with individuals. He regards others merely as subjects for observation and/or alteration. He indulges his caprices to an excess, resulting in self-destructive behavior. (Mukherjee 118) He encounters his own fortitude in Bhudeb Roy. He is similarly cynical. Alu, the central character, is the nephew of Balaram. He is the sole survivor of the family. The subsequent section of the novel narrates a different story. A pragmatic and spirited trader efforts to unite the Indian population in the Middle East. However, these efforts ultimately demonstrate impracticality. The final section narrates the tale of Mrs. Verma, who unequivocally dismisses rational thought. She once more endeavours to establish an Indian form of communal existence in the desert. However, Alu, Zindi, and Iyoti Das, a police officer, abandon Mrs. Verma and her experiments in the desert. At the conclusion of the narrative, these three individuals are in pursuit of new horizons, unshaped aspirations, and concepts. Hope constitutes their sole asset.

Ghosh adeptly illustrated the challenges faced by women during migration in a worldwide context through this novel. This narrative compellingly presents a bleak examination of the repressive regimes of movement, where reason and resources become metonymic and just circulating forces in the world. Brinda Bose (2000) writes:

"The Circle of Reason offers an allegorical lens on migration, capturing the perpetual human search for roots while navigating displacement" (104).

The novel focuses on a disparate assembly of vagrants from various regions of India on the fictional island of al-Ghazira and in Algeria, highlighting the quest for meaning among those whose lives are impacted by globalization and whose very bodies endure the harsh and

brutal realities of this journey and history. The section labeled "Quieted" is the most significant and remarkable in conveying Ghosh's concept of the ghost of Globalization. This passage conveys the unique lives, aspirations, and desires of the travelers on the unstable vessel, Mariamma, transporting them to al-Ghazira as migrant workers. 'Mariam' is the South Indian equivalent of Mary, whereas Mariamma refers to Mother Mary, incorporating the term 'amma'. They are generally the commencement for al-Ghazira, a thriving maritime hub of commerce and trade. The protagonist, Alu, is evading a crude Indian police force and an absurd allegation stemming from a trivial and inconsequential altercation between his 'rational' uncle Balaram and the traditional and corrupt local landowner Bhudeb Roy. Zindi is a 'madam' who operates a brothel in al-Ghazira after being expelled from her marital residence by her husband and in-laws due to her infertility. Karthamma and Kulfi have been selected by Zindi to serve as prostitutes there. Rakesh is a former traveling marketer of Ayurvedic medicine, which he would never sell. Samuel, an educator, is a man who articulates conjectures regarding lines and other subjects.

The condition and arrangement of Mariamma's female workers exemplify the disparities in opportunities faced by transients, highlighting issues of mistreatment, hardship, and misfortune. The meticulous and cautionary Professor Samuel perceives the Indian women traveling to al-Ghazira to work as prostitutes in Zindi's residence as confined and subjugated individuals: "She is a madam... . If she were not, what would be the reason for her to gather these unfortunate women across the ocean? What rationale would lead her to confine them closely, akin to detainees in the lodge? I inform you that she will relocate them into bondage in al-Ghazira.

That is a relevant point. Alternatively, it may be considered worse. Conversely, Zindi articulates her perspective: "she not only perceives herself as assisting the women, but she also insists that their relationships are familial rather than transactional. (173

Regarding women, upon my arrival in India, I will not be required to undertake any responsibilities.

These women seek me out and approach swiftly. Take me, Zindi-no, me, Zindi-didi—do not take her, as she has lice. They continue in that manner. However, I do not accept all of them. I select only those who are virtuous—neat, courteous, and diligent.

Therefore, I must travel to India personally to investigate. The entirety of al-Ghazira

recognizes that Zindi's girls are dependable and industrious. I receive a modest additional amount, but it is not excessive. It is not merely a business; it represents my family, my household, and I take responsibility for all members, both male and female, ensuring their well-being and fostering a loving environment. (181)

Zindi's prompt verbal response is particularly noteworthy for its consistent characterization of prostitution as a form of "work" and the women involved as "diligent employees," reflecting an effort to legitimize both female sex work and her own business practices. This flag seeks to frame prostitution as a profitable occupation, aiming to acknowledge it and clarify its role as a significant component of the global economy. Furthermore, the intrigue surrounding the naming of the women and their contributions, as well as the relationship between Zindi and the female migrant workers, highlights the complex interplay between domestic and labor spheres. This phenomenon is not only evident in cases of prostitution but also extends to familial and social networks. This approach illustrates how the movement of these women encompasses the loss of home, while the ongoing demand for simplicity necessitates the integration of the spatial dimensions of home and work, domestic and public, private and open.

Furthermore, it is crucial to acknowledge Zindi's intense desire to understand the relationship of trade between them as simultaneously a connection of mutual affection and shared bonds. For a woman who is excluded from her own Indian diaspora and her marital home due to isolation, the sex work industry becomes an alternative form of productivity that creates a substitute family for her. Capital provides Zindi with a sense of plainness or belongingness that her male-centric social network and family exclude her from. The framework of male-centric brutality facilitates biased representations of the female body, resulting in a significant disconnection of femininity from abstract recognition. In this manner, it is negotiated through the experience of residing in a surrogate home, where she interacts with transient female sex workers.

Consequently, due to the abrupt changes in Alu's life, he is compelled to relinquish his affection for Maya Debi, daughter of Shombu Debnath. Alu, feeling unacknowledged in his desire for a conjugal life, abruptly expresses his feelings to his uncle Balaram.

"I desire ...," Alu stated, "I wish to enter into marriage..." I am already acquainted with someone.

A female individual, that is what I refer to. Are you implying...? Balaram regarded him with incredulity. Are you referring to love? A marriage based on love? Alu exhibited significant embarrassment, responding with a strained voice. I intend to marry Maya. Maya Debnath. (112-113)

Nonetheless, Alu is not married to Maya. Designated as a formidable psychological militant, he is permitted to depart from Lalpukur. From this point on, Ghosh elucidates the intrigue and quest for self-preservation amidst chaos and turmoil. Alu begins to exist on the precipice of life.

Jyoti Das, an Assistant Superintendent of Police, is informed about Alu and his alleged fear-mongering campaign. Alu hastens to Calcutta, subsequently travels to Kerala, and ultimately proceeds by boat to al-Ghazira. Simultaneously, he is being pursued by the police from a distance. He must even relinquish traveling by buses and plans to evade capture. He traverses the Nilgiri forests. His life proves to be remarkably extraordinary and disconnected from that of ordinary humans. His nomadic disposition and propensity for escapism render him brave, while complicating his ability to confront the trials and tribulations of life.

Ghosh vividly illustrates the suffering and perseverance of overlooked laborers in distant countries who consistently endure a nomadic lifestyle. Through the remarkable lens of new historicism, Ghosh elucidates the challenges faced by transient professionals who anticipate benevolence from an institution and profession that remains perpetually elusive. Personality, in an emotional context, represents an empowering equality and congruity of the 'authentic self' or 'internal voice,' which shapes and constructs one's inner character. In contemporary usage, character denotes the resemblance to others while yet possessing traits that distinguish one from the others. Tabish Khair (2001) writes:

"In Ghosh's hands, the personal becomes political as his characters traverse globalized spaces, presenting a critique of bureaucratic systems that erode individuality" (69).

For instance, Alu possesses a pervasive character and also a more distinctive and unique personal identity. Character maintains a continuous balance between similarity and difference despite personal development and evolving social circumstances. These changes suggest that the individual engages in self-reflection, seeking change to fulfill an internal desire for stability. Alu, as a whole and in individual components, is not segmented into distinct roles and responsibilities; it engages in a multifaceted and often tumultuous public life while maintaining

consistency and integrity at all levels. Ultimately, an individual's personality evolves into a social character, which then transforms into a national character, culminating in a comprehensive global perspective. Individuals with a clear theme partitioned their selves to ascertain their identity, purpose, and direction. In challenging and distressing situations, there is a loss of integrity that results in a crisis.

The narrative unfolds in a town called Lalpukur, where a child attains his objective with the assistance of his relative, Toru-debi. The child's head is notably distinct from that of an ordinary person; yet, it is abnormally large with numerous bumps and irregularities. The child is named Alu due to the peculiar condition of his skull, as designated by his uncle, Balaram. Alu is the central character in the narrative, through whom all the events are observed.

The mythology of *The Circle of Reason* pertains to Nachiketa Bose, who is referred to as Alu, signifying "potato." This is due to the condition of his head, which is uneven, coarse, and quite large. A restrained hero is not unusual in a certain form of enchanted authenticity. He embarks on a journey of creative energy that unfolds from a foundation of misguided tenacity as Alu's uncle Balaram employs phrenology convincingly to undermine him. The assortment of contusions and swellings proliferated uniformly across his head, offering no indications of differentiation into distinct and identifiable organs. It was remarkably perplexing and highly stimulating due to a plethora of new, exciting content. Eventually, it prompted Balaram's discourse on the ambiguity of the cerebral organs.

Ghosh illustrated this tale with his characteristic magical realism, illuminating numerous compelling themes related to India during that period and the lives of the scholars. Balaram perceived Alu's head as distinct from others due to its numerous contusions, which caused him much distress. He perceived his mind as a fusion of demand and controversy. Alu is consistently a reserved individual. He does not freely articulate his thoughts and feelings with his uncle, Balaram. Alu never conveyed his preferences to his uncle. He frequently visited Rakhali's father, Shombu Debnath, where he observed him calmly at his weaving machines. While he wove a material, Alu observed him and his craft with great diligence. At that juncture, he was motivated by excellence and sought to master the art of weaving. Balaram subsequently felt exceedingly pleased as he exhibited a notable interest for acquiring an artwork. He proposed that it is a captivating artwork that is connected to the rationale. Balaram remarked:

Thus, weaving embodies hope; a vibrant conviction that, having unified the world, it has sanctified its diversity. It must repeat this action. Weaving embodies optimism since it transcends national and continental boundaries. Weaving is the rationale that drives the world to madness and imbues it with humanity. (58)

The lengthy first section of the novel depicts Alu, an apprentice weaver under the skilled Shombu Debnath, while his uncle Balaram, the esteemed local educator influenced by Western ideologies, is characterized by his fascination with phrenology and the writings of Louis Pasteur. In his enthusiasm to present his unexpected yet conventional logical theory, he organizes the Pasteur School of Reason, where he addresses the topic of Reason and undertakes efforts to sanitize the town using carbolic acid. He engages Shombu Debnath to demonstrate weaving, while his spouse exhibits sewing and stitching. His fixation on carbolic corrosive and his adversarial relationship with Bhudeb Roy, the owner of the local school, leads to his downfall, along with others, except for Alu, who embarks on the remainder of his journey to other areas of the world.

Balaram is entirely preoccupied with rationale and orderliness. Without delay, he became a legend at Presidency College for his advocacy of clean dress. Similarly, at Lalpukur, he commenced his struggle against the pathogens. This news ultimately reached Jyothi Das, who was investigating the particulars of the Balaram case as a radical.

Subsequently, it became a conundrum; Jyothi Das became ensnared in that labyrinth of causality. During the composition of his report, he discovered a newspaper clipping within the file, a discoloured fragment of paper, perhaps placed there by a diligent clerk. Educator confronts pathogens, preserves countless lives. The report asserted that Lalpukur remained free of germs while numerous other border villages were afflicted by sickness, due to the endeavours of Balaram Bose, a teacher, who inundated the area with antiseptic. (83)

This work similar to Ghosh's other works, dismisses the fundamental distinctions between tradition and innovation, as well as between isolated Eastern and Western societies. The historical context of weaving and the worldwide textile framework persistently recurs in this and all of his subsequent works. It becomes a proverb of the perplexing system of incongruities in which all cultures are ensnared and closely linked with their neighbours. When Balaram decides to mentor the young Alu, a weaver, he persuades him by referencing the

historical development of weaving and how it reflects the responsibility of societal instability and permeable boundaries due to cross-border borrowings. As stated by Balaram:

The loom has formed a singular reality, as it has consistently disallowed any division of existence. The loom acknowledges neither continents nor nations. It has united the planet. (55)

Balaram articulates and reinforces the notion that society is a continuum of progress that transcends national boundaries through many techniques. Weaving constitutes the basis of this concept, and he cites the instance of global fabric exchange, which traverses every conceivable pathway despite societal disparities and nuances as follows:

Indian textiles were discovered in the tombs of the pharaohs. Indian soil is littered with fabric from China. The entirety of the ancient world thrived on the textile trade. The Silk Route, originating in China and traversing Central Asia and Persia to the Mediterranean, subsequently extending to the markets of Africa and Europe, interconnected continents for countless centuries. Throughout these epochs, textiles, in their opulence and diversity, linked the Mediterranean to Asia, India to Africa, and the Arab world to Europe in a mutually prosperous trade. (55-56)

The history of weaving lacks precise national origins, yet it adeptly traverses complex worldwide pathways. It can be examined as a high-quality example of traditional craftsmanship in contrast to Western technology and innovation. These graphic questions the notion of remarkable divisions among cultures and nations. Weaving is not always the most effective necessity in the story; yet, various other techniques persist throughout the narrative, imposing a semblance of order on a chaotic universe.

This novel evokes a sensation that is remarkably influenced by Pasteur. Balaram perceives Alu as significantly lacking in enthusiasm. He recites a paragraph from the e-book to illustrate Pasteur's courage in administering an untested rabies vaccine to a 10-year-old boy who had been bitten by a rabid dog.

Alu weeps at the conclusion of the passage. However, at a different event, it was Alu who salvaged this e-book from the fireplace incident. This e-book plays a vital role in fostering intimacy and a positive relationship between Balaram and Alu. During an occasion when Alu seeks refuge in Gopal's area, Gopal provides him with several outfits, some currency, and a

copy of the book titled Life of Pasteur. Alu, in conjunction with this e-book, significantly impacts Mariamma without reading it; nonetheless, certain pages support Karthamma, who refuses to provide the child without signing documents. Subsequently, Prof. Samuel shreds the pages and presents them to her for signature. The duplicate of Gopal's book is located in Al-Ghazira. Subsequently, Alu discovers the copy of Life of Pasteur in Mrs. Verma's collection. It became a duplicate of Dantu, which was perfected for Dantu by Balaram. This booklet concludes the entire cycle. Mrs. Verma and Alu incinerate the ebook alongside Kulfi's deceased body, symbolizing the completion of the cycle.

Returning to Alu's narrative, we observe him becoming intensely engaged in his uncle's scheme to sanitize the refugee encampments with carbolic acid. However, at the level of human motivations, the cleaning effort targets Bhudeb Roy. The initiative aims to eradicate microorganisms. Balram, representing reason, has a natural adversary in Bhudeb Roy, who promotes a personality cult and engages in irrational behaviours.

Consequently, the campaign to eradicate pathogens transforms into the campaign to eliminate Bhudeb and his kind. However, events unfold in their own manner. A catastrophic fire obliterates Balram, his residence, and the educational institution. Bhudeb Roy identifies Alu as a convenient scapegoat. Bhudeb designates Alu as a notorious terrorist. From this juncture, the perilous existence of Alu commences. He commences to exist on the precipice of normalcy. Jyoti Das, an Assistant Superintendent of Police, is informed about Alu and his purported terrorist actions. Alu hastens to Calcutta, subsequently travels to Kerala, and ultimately proceeds by boat to Al-Ghazira. Throughout, he is pursued by the cops. He was compelled to forgo traveling by buses and trains; he traverses the Nilgiri forests. Alu's existence deviates from the conventional. The presence of cops consistently amplifies the excitement of his escapade. The itinerant nature of this narrative becomes evident.

The narrative of Alu serves not only as a critique of contemporary civilization's lack of roots but also provides the reader with an opportunity for adventure. Established in the habitual patterns of our existence, Alu's narrative ignites creativity. Adventure, threat, and danger are deeply rooted in the human psyche. Alu's narrative provides an opportunity to experience or revisit that aspect of our mind. It is an illustration of a life devoid of a central focus. Individuals intrigued by nihilistic pleasures may conduct an insightful Derridian analysis of this book. However, that is not to my preference, particularly not at this time.

Balram embodies rationality. The relevance of an action to contemporary circumstances is his sole criterion for evaluating matters and individuals. The interplay between reason and religion presents a comprehensive discourse in this work. Balram is captivated by the book, 'Life of Pasteur.' Pasteur represents his ideal; logic embodies his deity. His sole objective in life is rational reasoning. However, the author possesses the maturity to highlight the limitations of reason in practical contexts. The scientific temper and the theory of causality are ineffective in practical scenarios.

Balram's situation exemplifies the rigor of reasoning. He is unable to transcend reason. It ought to be entirely sensible, and it must be for him. He cannot tolerate even the slightest deviation from the upright, linear, and immutable logical course. Consequently, Balram's plans are consistently disrupted upon implementation. The narrative commences with his youth. He aspired to pursue research and emulate distinguished scientists such as Pasteur and Jagdish Bose. However, his instructors at Dhaka determine that he excels in history and refer him to Dr. Radhakrishnan, the Philosophy professor at Presidency College, Calcutta. In Calcutta, his preferred pastime is to examine heads. He frequently encounters difficulties due to his compulsive tendency to scrutinize and critique others' appearances.

However, Balram possesses a resilient character. His steadfast commitment to rationality as the sole philosophy of life earns him a lifelong buddy, Gopal. He is also affiliated with a rationalist organization. However, Gopal, despite his closest friend's intuition of impending trouble, experienced a foreboding: a foreboding of the calamity he would inflict upon himself and others if he were ever permitted to assume control of the society. He resolved, with unusual resolve, to do every effort to prevent it from occurring' (50). In a similar manner, Balram's wife likewise perceives wrongdoing and incinerates his books. Alu can preserve only one book, 'Life of Pasteur.' 'Life of Pasteur' serves as a prominent emblem in this tale. However, before to addressing that, let us see how astutely Ghosh juxtaposes prophesy with rationality. The rationality of Balram is contrasted with the foreboding of his well-wishers, contradictory forces are at play. Is it not a fundamental aspect of existence? Life cannot be categorized as merely dichotomous. Ghosh is an adept writer as his writings present a balanced perspective on conflicting themes. Premonitions materialize, although rationality persists. Motivated by this book, Balram establishes a school in his community named 'School of Reason.' This represents the definitive examination of his long-held aspirations for rationality.

The book is rather complex to understand. Upon Alu's initial introduction in the novel, Balram expresses concern regarding Alu's lack of reaction. He instructs Alu with fervent enthusiasm. Alu listens to him in rapt silence. Balram is moved. He reads from the text and pauses to observe tears in Alu's eyes. As Alu rescues the book from the fire, it becomes Balram's moment to be tearful. The book serves as a connection between uncle and nephew, perpetuating the heritage of reason throughout generations. The paramount achievement for a rationalist is to persuade another individual to adopt their perspective. This logic engages in a battle against pathogens, which are the source of all ailments. The comparison can be extended, wherein carbolic acid, as an instrument of scientific rigour, makes an effort to eradicate diseases, while reason, as a cognitive derivative of scientific rigor, seeks to eliminate societal evils. The many cleansing procedures serve as a metaphor throughout the story. In *Al-Ghazira*, Hajji Fahmy compels Adil and his cousin to cleanse themselves with antiseptic.

Carbolic acid is integral to Alu's cleaning regimen. Near the conclusion of the tale, Mrs. Verma is depicted utilizing carbolic acid in place of Ganga Jal. Dr. Mishra observes, 'Carbolic acid has transformed into sacred water' (411). Mrs. Verma responds, 'What difference does it make if it is Ganga Jal or Carbolic acid?' (411)

It merely pertains to tidying the location, correct? Perceptions of cleanliness have shifted; what was formerly considered clean is now viewed differently. What significance does it hold for the deceased, Dr. Mishra? (411). Ghosh is highlighting the unquestioning faith of millions of Indians in Ganga Jal, despite the severe pollution of the life-giving river's water. The book 'Life of Pasteur' is also pertinent to Mrs. Verma's life. Her father introduced her to the book, which ultimately inspired her to become a microbiologist. The narrative concludes with Kulfu's demise, despite Balram and Alu's attempts to prevent it. This represents a failure of reason, as the chosen path of action lacks rationality. The text asserts, '...without the germ, life would become impossible because death would be incomplete' (396).

The work comprises three sections that address the turmoil and uncertainty in the life of Alu, the protagonist. Alu arrives in Lalpukur to reside with his uncle, Balaram, in the initial segment, and in the subsequent segment, Alu flees from the secret police officer, Jyoti Das, who attempts to apprehend him as a most wanted terrorist. The initial segment concludes when their residence is detonated. This section mostly examines the comic characters Alu and Balaram, highlighting Balaram's fluctuating fascinations with phrenology, pedagogy, and subsequently, the Pasteurian initiative to purify the city with carbolic acid. Ultimately, they also

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establish a school founded on voluntary efforts, while Balaram undertakes his germ-fighting initiative. One may contest this perspective, namely about Bhudeb-Roy, the region's corrupt politician, who, with the assistance of national officials, effectively demolishes Balaram and his residence.

The moneyless society is obliterated not just by municipal and national authorities but also by neo-imperialist oil dealers. In addition to establishing a capitalism vs socialist experiment within the narrative, the concept from the first half is reiterated. The subalterns can assert agency; however, when they do, the authorities promptly respond to suppress and constrain such activity. The outcome in both instances is mortality. This highlights that the marginalized society may attempt to seize agency, although at the expense of its existence. Life and security are in risk of vanishing and extinction anytime the characters attempt to communicate. Characters must either perish, sustain injuries, or be compelled to escape for their survival. The vulnerable are the focus of their oppressors, and we can hear their voices despite attempts to stifle them. (Hawley 45) Ghosh articulates his concerns regarding the vulnerabilities of the weaker entities and the hegemonies that constrain them, asserting that he will subsequently demonstrate how this theme is further examined in *The Calcutta Chromosome*, which can be regarded as the inaugural novel in which Amitav Ghosh is fully articulate and expressive about the subordinate counter-order.

Amitav Ghosh adeptly illustrated the challenges and dilemmas faced by immigrant women in a worldwide context in this novel. The story presents a bleak examination of the oppressions of migration, wherein reason and resources transform into metonymic and just circulating forces within the world. Concentrating on a diverse cohort of migrants originating from various regions of India to a fictitious island named al-Ghazira and Algeria. The novel thus explores the quest for significance among individuals displaced by globalization, whose bodies bear the violent and terrible scars of this journey and its history.

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